

Bias Mitigation in Machine Learning Models for Recidivism Using Explainable AI

Aagnya Mistry^{3†}, Jaiwin Mehta^{2†}, Ankit Datta^{2†},
Agam Kamdar^{1†}, Neha Katre^{1*†}, Sweedle Machado^{1†}

^{1*}Department of Information Technology, Dwarkadas J. Sanghvi College of Engineering, Vile Parle, Mumbai, 400056, Maharashtra, India.

²Department of Computer Engineering, Dwarkadas J. Sanghvi College of Engineering, Vile Parle, Mumbai, 400056, Maharashtra, India.

³Department of Computer Science and Engineering (Data Science), Dwarkadas J. Sanghvi College of Engineering, Vile Parle, Mumbai, 400056, Maharashtra, India.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): neha.mendjoge@djsce.ac.in;

Contributing authors: aagnya.mistry@gmail.com;

jwinmehta@gmail.com; dattankit@gmail.com;

agamkamdargdsce@gmail.com; sweedle.machado@djsce.ac.in;

[†]These authors contributed equally to this work.

Abstract

Criminal recidivism is a significant public safety issue, with offenders released from prison regularly re-offending. In an attempt to prevent it, risk assessment tools driven by machine learning are heavily employed. But most machine learning models suffer from bias towards sensitive features like gender and race. This research compares the performance and fairness of four Machine Learning models, Logistic Regression, Support Vector Classifier, Gradient Boosting Classifier, and XGBoost on ProPublica's COMPAS data set. SHapley Additive ExPlanations (SHAP) analysis determined prior count, sex, age, and race as the primary predictive features. Further fairness assessments with Fairlearn indicated group-level imbalances. In order to counter these, both in-processing and post-processing debiasing strategies were applied. Adversarial Debiasing was employed as the in-processing method, while post-processing methods were Reject Option Classification, Equalized Odds, and Calibrated Equalized Odds. These were effective in minimizing bias with zero loss in accuracy. Across all models that were tested, Support Vector Classifier had the best trade-off between fairness and accuracy

and always offered high prediction performance as well as equitable results across groups protected, as reflected by Disparate Impact values (1.0012 (Sex) & 0.9163 (Race)) and overall accuracy (68.26 (Sex) & 67.22(Race)).

Keywords: artificial intelligence, crime prediction, explainable artificial intelligence, machine learning, recidivism

1 Introduction

Crime is a continuing threat to the well-being of society, eroding safety and public confidence. Among the biggest challenges for criminal justice is recidivism—the recidivistic behavior of individuals with prior convictions to commit new offenses. Recidivism increasingly overburdens social systems and reduces the return on rehabilitation investments. Research is continually shown to prove that convicts with past convictions are statistically more likely to recidivate (Gendreau et al. 1996). Crime prevention activities everywhere are thus a grave concern in combating recidivism.

Predictive instruments for gauging recidivism risk have engulfed the globe in an attempt to enable more informed decisions in the realm of parole, sentencing, and rehabilitation programs. With the advanced machine learning capacity, instruments employed to assess the risk of recidivism have expanded significantly to be more data-driven and automated (Zhang 2022). However, although ML models promise predictive effectiveness, they are often plagued by entrenched bias, especially against protected traits such as race and gender. Bias in this type can result in skewed outcomes and severe ethical problems in high-stakes domains like criminal justice.

Observing these constraints, more recent work has discovered a still larger focus on the incorporation of explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) into criminal recidivism prediction models to serve the ends of enhancing transparency and fairness (Ersöz et al. 2025). It is not just optimized accuracy that is the goal but model decisions explainable and auditable for possible discrimination (Wang et al. 2022). Through an understanding of how features influence predictions, practitioners can more effectively identify and reduce bias (Rudin et al. 2020).

This research adds to this existing discussion by comparing four machine learning models on a public dataset stated further. Both predictive performance and fairness analysis are given prime importance. Explainability of the models is also studied through SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) for global feature attribution (Lundberg and Lee 2017), and Fairlearn (Bird et al. 2020), used for group-level disparities and informing fairness interventions. Together, this work uniquely addresses both predictive performance and ethical considerations, distinguishing itself from prior research.

With regard to prior publication, some elements of the methodology, especially the application of XAI methods to recidivism prediction, have been briefly described in conference proceedings. Yet, this paper extensively builds on those early findings by incorporating a thorough fairness analysis and providing an elaborate comparison

between the four machine learning models. The added depth and range of investigation render this research a significant extension over prior presentations. However, it is important to recognize that explanations from biased models may inadvertently perpetuate unfairness (Jain et al. 2020).

This paper presents a systematic method of predicting recidivism with machine learning models, i.e.: XGBoost (XGB), Support Vector Classifier (SVC), Gradient Boosted Decision Trees (GBDT), and Logistic Regression. The approach includes preprocessing the Correctional Offender Management Profiling for Alternative Sanctions (COMPAS) data set (Angwin et al. 2016), model training, the inclusion of in-processing and post-processing techniques for fairness improvement, and Fairlearn and SHAP analysis for the explainability of the models.

The COMPAS data set contains data about identification information, demographic characteristics, criminal history information, current offense information, reoffense markers, and risk scores. This makes it an ideal data set for research on fairness and bias in prediction models.

In-processing approaches incorporated during the model training time by revising the fairness constraints and adapting the learning algorithm itself are designed to minimize bias. Post-processing approaches, in contrast, make fairness corrections after the model has generated predictions, acting on the output only and not the model.

To assess both the predictive and ethical considerations, particularly targeting two protected characteristics: Sex and Race, the research workflow as a whole is designed thoughtfully. Due to the social and historical prejudices in actual observations, it is critical to incorporate these protected attributes. If ignored, they can adversely affect marginalized groups through algorithmic judgments in the criminal justice system. This research seeks to advance transparent recidivism prediction systems.

The whole process is crafted with caution to quantify both predictive and ethical factors, specifically aiming at the two protected features: Sex and Race. These protected features need to be taken into account, since, according to existing literature and social experience in the real world, ignoring them may disproportionately impact marginalized groups through algorithmic results in the justice system. By targeting these aspects, this study seeks to assist in developing more equitable and transparent recidivism prediction systems.

2 Methodology

2.1 Data set

The study aimed to use the widely known COMPAS data set, originally developed by Northpointe (now known as Equivant), and analyzed in 2016 by ProPublica, an independent nonprofit organization focused on investigative journalism. The data set includes information on defendants from Broward County, Florida, who were assessed using the COMPAS risk scoring system. It has been a key resource in the study of algorithmic fairness, mainly in the criminal justice system.

Other researchers (Barenstein 2019) assert that ProPublica committed a data preprocessing error since it applied the two year sample rule of thumb for non-recidivists but not for recidivists, making the data set biased towards having a higher number

of recidivists than it would otherwise. But ProPublica’s data processing strategy - keeping those who were observed for at least two years or those who recidivate within two years - seems biased on its face, but it can be considered a sensible and practical option based on what the analysis is trying to do. The ultimate goal of the data set is to compare the predictive validity of COMPAS risk scores over a two-year period. From this view, including individuals who recidivate within two years, whether they had the full two-year observation window or not, ensures that all applicable recidivism events during that time are included.

Omitting those who recidivate within two years simply because they hadn’t yet reached the two-year point would throw away useful outcome data, resulting in unnecessary information loss. On the other hand, limiting the analysis to only non-recidivists who were tracked for the entire two years prevents mistakenly classifying an individual as a non-recidivist when they just hadn’t had time to recidivate. Therefore, while the data set becomes censored for certain subjects, this logic of asymmetry serves to preserve label fidelity, which is particularly important for training and testing supervised learning models. For this reason, under the requirement of preserving correct results for the two-year time period, ProPublica’s methodology can be seen as a pragmatic compromise but not a root bias. Thus, this study uses ProPublica’s version of the data set for analysis.

The data set covers aspects clustered into categories such as identification details, demographic attributes, criminal history, current offence data, reoffend indicators, and risk assessment scores.

Since, the data set was in raw format, incapable for a machine to be able to interpret it, the research is next followed by preprocessing techniques. The research followed a structured approach to identify the biases in the machine learning models described in the Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Workflow: data acquiring, pre-processing, model training, mitigation of bias, and evaluation

2.2 Preprocessing

The first step towards achieving the goal of the research is pre-processing. In this step, the data set was imported directly into the Google Colab file for data acquisition. This study uses ProPublica's COMPAS Revisited data set instead of the AIF360 library, as it underwent critical bias corrections that addressed an error in the original data set where recidivists with less than 2 years of observation were improperly included. Though the AIF360 library provides a convenient version of the COMPAS data set, it probably did not include the particular bias corrections. Hence, ProPublica's updated version is taken as the more accurate and least biased one for recidivism.

Raw data set has 53 features (columns) and 7,214 records (rows). During initial review, the data set had a number of columns with irrelevant data, null values, inconsistency in data type, and redundant entries. The data cleaning was done by eliminating irrelevant columns like personal ID, name, date, and charge description as these variables fluctuated between records and might be confusing to make predictions. Columns such as sex and race were one-hot encoded, i.e., for each distinct value in these categories, a new column was formed consisting of binary values (0 or 1) to represent the presence or absence of each category.

The research also tried to encode charge description values, in the hope that they could help with the prediction. However, this did not improve model performance, and thus, these encoded features were excluded from the data set. After dropping irrelevant columns, the data set was rechecked, and no missing values or duplicates were found.

2.3 Data Visualization

Next, the data set was visualized using a correlation heat map (Fig. 2). The following key correlations were observed:

Note: Fig. 2 displays a correlation heatmap with only the variables that were found to be relevant throughout the study. The variables that were found to be irrelevant through the analysis were not included and are not shown in the heatmap.

Fig. 2 Correlation heatmap of demographic and criminal history features

- The juvenile offense-related characteristics (`juv_fel_count`, `juv_misd_count`, `juv_other_count`) showed moderate to high intercorrelation, indicating the possibility of multicollinearity. However, only keeping the aggregated feature `priors_count` had a negative effect on accuracy; thus, the original features were retained as is.
- A very high correlation between `is_recid` (recidivism indicator) and both `priors_count` (criminal history of defendant) and `two_year_recid` (recidivism within 2 years) suggested that prior criminal behavior of a defendant is a significant predictor for future recidivism.
- The “`c_charge_degree_M`” feature, although showing a weak negative correlation, was retained in the dataset as it proved to be useful, especially when combined with other features.

For the target variables, the data set included “`two_year_recid`” and “`is_recid`”. Both indicate whether a defendant has committed a crime within a specific period of time, but there was an overlap between these features. When the data overlap was checked, the following observations were concluded (Fig. 3):

Fig. 3 Two_year_recid and is_recid overlap heatmap

- The top-left cell (3743) shows the number of people who did not re-offend within two years of their COMPAS screening ($\text{two_year_recid} = 0$) and also did not re-offend at all before the end of data collection ($\text{is_recid} = 0$).
- The top-right cell (220) indicates individuals who did not re-offend within two years ($\text{two_year_recid} = 0$) but did re-offend at some later point during the data collection period ($\text{is_recid} = 1$).
- The bottom-left cell (0) shows that no individuals re-offended within two years without also being flagged as having re-offended during the data collection period — meaning $\text{two_year_recid} = 1$ implies $\text{is_recid} = 1$.
- The bottom right cell (3251) represents individuals who re-offended within two years of screening ($\text{two_year_recid} = 1$); thus by default it means they re-offended before the end of data collection ($\text{is_recid} = 1$).

This indicates very little mismatch between is_recid and two_year_recid yet all the models in this study were trained and tested on both target columns. This study does not consider the is_violent_recid column as a target variable because it has a very high class imbalance in its distribution. There are 6,395 individuals who did not recidivate violently at release, while there are only 819 individuals who did. This implies that cases of violent recidivism are less than 12(percent sign) of all observations. This kind of imbalance can cause biased training of models, where predictions become skewed toward the majority class leading to potentially high accuracy but poor real-world performance on the minority class. This is dangerous in fairness-sensitive applications, where under representation of some outcomes can have critical ethical consequences.

The data set was then split into training and testing data sets using a train-test split of 80:20, i.e., (80% for training, 20% for testing). Four machine learning models — XG Boost, Support Vector Classifier (SVC), Logistic Regression, Gradient

Boosted Decision Trees (GBDT) – were trained separately on the target variables (“is_recid”, ”two_year_recid”).

2.4 Models

The sole aim of this research was to compare different machine learning models, ranging from simple to complicated, in order to figure out which of them are most suitable to learn patterns from the recidivism data set (Rudin 2019). To achieve this goal, we choose four classifiers: Logistic Regression (LogReg), Support Vector Classifier (SVC), Gradient Boosting Decision Trees (GBDT), and XGBoost (XGB).

2.4.1 Logistic Regression

The Logistic Regression model is a strong baseline for binary classification tasks, in which the goal is to predict one of two classes (e.g., “yes/no” or “0/1”). Being a linear model, it tries to find the best hyperplane (or line in two dimensional case) that can split the data into its two classes. The model gives a weight to every feature, and the ultimate prediction is calculated from a linear combination of the weights. The decision boundary is defined by the threshold value of the sigmoid function, such that any prediction above the threshold is classified as “1” or “yes,” and any prediction below the threshold is labeled as “0” or “no.”

Fig. 4 Figure 4(a) illustrates the confusion matrix for the Logistic Regression model with the target variable two_year_recid, while Figure 4(b) presents the confusion matrix for the same model using is_recid as the target variable

First, the model was trained with default parameters as stated in the documentation: $C = 1.0$ and solver = ‘lbfgs’. In these parameters, the model performed with 68.32% accuracy. The C parameter determines the strength of regularization, with lower values denoting stronger regularization. The solver parameter determines the algorithm employed for optimization during the training process. To further enhance the performance of the model, RandomizedSearchCV was used in a hyperparameter

optimization. The parameter grid to be searched was $C = \text{np.logspace}(-2, 2, 5)$ and $\text{solver} = [\text{'liblinear'}, \text{'saga'}]$.

Upon using this optimization method, the optimally performing hyperparameters were found to be $\text{solver} = \text{'liblinear'}$ and $C = 0.01$ (converted to $\text{np.float64}(0.01)$), with a slightly better accuracy of 68.88%. Although accuracy dipped slightly, the hyperparameter tuning is useful for providing insights into model optimization and regularization for binary classification tasks.

2.4.2 Support Vector Classifier

On the other hand, Support Vector Classifier (SVC) is a more advanced model that learns more complex decision boundaries. When a model cannot separate the data using a simple line, it does so by finding the best boundary or hyperplane that separates the categories in the feature space. It aims to maximize the margin, which is the distance between the categories, and the nearest data points from each category, are called support vectors. The key advantage of SVC is its ability to handle non-linearly separable data (i.e., if the data is not linearly separable in the original feature space) by using a kernel trick. The kernel function transforms the features into an n-dimensional space where the linear separation may be possible. Common kernel functions are linear kernel, polynomial kernel, and Radial Bias Function (rbf) kernel.

The research initially used the Radial Bias Function (rbf) kernel (the default kernel in the documentation), which gave us an accuracy of 69.23%. Later on, after fine tuning the model's performance through hyperparameter optimization, where the parameters were C (Regularization parameter), kernel and gamma. The C parameter controls the trade-off between maximizing the margin and minimizing the classification error. A higher value of C can be stricter on the errors in the training data making the model more prone to overfitting, while a lower value of C can ignore the errors in the training data leading to a simpler, less complex decision boundary.

Fig. 5 Figure 5(a) illustrates the confusion matrix for the Support Vector Classifier model with the target variable `two_year_recid`, while Figure 5(b) presents the confusion matrix for the same model using `is_recid` as the target variable

The model in this research was trained on C values of (0.1, 1, 10 and 50). The kernel function, as explained before, allows for the linear separation of classes that are not linearly separable in the original space. The kernel functions used for this research on the SVC model were ('linear', 'rbf', 'poly'). The gamma parameter, on the other hand, defines the influence of each training example on the decision boundary. A higher gamma value makes the model more sensitive to individual data points, leading to overfitting, while a lower gamma value makes the model generalized. The gamma values on which the model was trained were (0.001, 0.01, 0.1 and 1).

After applying RandomizedSearchCV for hyperparameter optimization, we identified the most suitable combination of these parameters. The fine-tuned model achieved an accuracy of 69.50% on the test data set. The best parameters were found to be ["C" : 1, "kernel": "rbf", "gamma": 0.1].

2.4.3 Gradient Boosted Classifier

Gradient Boosted Classifier (GBC) is an ensemble technique that builds a series of decision trees, where each tree iteratively improves on errors made by previous trees. In a decision tree, the data is split based on specific features to predict the target variable. GBC improves by combining plenty such trees, where each tree is focused on fixing the errors of the previous ones. This method makes it adept at detecting complex, non-linear relationships in the data between features which interact in complicated ways.

Fig. 6 Figure 6(a) illustrates the confusion matrix for the Gradient Boosted Classifier model with the target variable two_year_recid, while Figure 6(b) presents the confusion matrix for the same model using is_recid as the target variable

Since GBC builds trees one after the other, it is more flexible and can achieve high accuracy. The parameters used in the model's hyperparameter optimization: n_estimators, learning_rate, max_depth, min_samples_split, min_samples_leaf and subsample. n_estimators specify the number of decision trees to be built by the model. A higher number of trees allow it to capture intricate patterns in the data, leading to

overfitting. `learning_rate` controls the contribution of each decision tree to the final prediction. A smaller learning rate value means each tree's contribution will be reduced, but more trees can be added to compensate for it. `max_depth` decides the maximum depth of each tree influencing the complexity of each decision tree. A higher depth value means capturing of detailed information leading to overfitting. `min_samples_split` parameter determines the minimum number of samples required to split an internal node. Higher values will prevent the model from branching based on very few samples, which would otherwise lead to overfitting. `min_samples_leaf` parameter controls the least minimum number of samples required to be a leaf node, ensuring that each leaf node represents a sufficient number of samples and is not specific to a particular data set. `subsample` represents the fraction of the data set used for fitting each decision tree being controlled by this parameter.

Initially, the model was trained using the default parameters given in the documentation of GBC, which are [`n_estimators` = 100, `learning_rate` = 0.1, `max_depth` = 3, `min_samples_split` = 2, `min_sample_leaf` = 1, `subsample` = 1.0] which gave an accuracy of 69.09%. Later on, a `RandomizedSearchCV` was applied to the model, which uses a random selection of combinations of these hyper parameters, evaluating them based on accuracy and integrating a cross-validation (`cv=3`) to ensure that the model is generalized.

After applying `RandomizedSearchCV`, the best estimators selected by the hyperparameter tuning method were (`n_estimators`: 50, `learning_rate`: 0.1, `max_depth`: 4, `min_samples_split`: 2, `min_sample_leaf`: 4, `subsample`: 0.6) which resulted in an accuracy of 68.81%.

2.4.4 XG Boost

XGBoost ([Chen and Guestrin 2016](#)) is a highly optimized version of Gradient Boosting model, capable of efficiently handling missing data, especially with large datasets, and modeling intricate feature interactions. Similar to GBC, it creates decision trees sequentially, but it places more emphasis on improving the weak areas and handling missing data effectively. One reason XGBoost is widely used is because it can efficiently manage complex feature relationships while maintaining computational efficiency, hence being extremely effective on large-scale problems ([Pangia et al. 2024](#)).

Fig. 7 Figure 7(a) illustrates the confusion matrix for the XG Boost model with the target variable `two_year_recid`, while Figure 7(b) presents the confusion matrix for the same model using `is_recid` as the target variable

The model was trained initially with the default parameters described in the documentation that yielded the accuracy of 67.35%. As, XGB is an optimized version of Gradient Boosting model, the parameters utilized hyper parameter tuning are similar to a great extent. The only parameter changed here is the `colsample_bytree` which is the subsample ratio of columns when building each tree. All the rest of the parameters are the same as the ones used in Gradient Boosted Classifier. Upon using `RandomizedSearchCV`, the best parameters were found to be, `n_estimators` : 100, `learning_rate` : 0.05, `max_depth` : 3, `subsample` : 0.6, `colsample_bytree` :0.8 These parameters gave a better accuracy of 68.88%.

Table 1 Initial accuracies and disparate impact values of classification models for protected variable (PV)

Models \ Metrics	Accuracies	Initial DI (PV: Sex)	Initial DI (PV: Race)
LogReg	68.88	3.2615	0.4504
SVC	69.50	1.8615	0.5546
GBDT	68.81	2.1701	0.5019
XGB	68.88	1.9409	0.4610

Note: A Disparate Impact (DI) value close to 1.0 indicates fairness in the model, while a DI far from it indicates potential bias.

All models were trained and tested on the same pre-processed dataset with the target variable as “`is_recid`” and “`two_year_recid`” as the target variables in individual experiments. The Table 1 and Table 2 depicts all the metrics with the target variable as “`is_recid`” and “`two_year_recid`”.

This set of linear (LogReg), margin-based (SVC), and tree-based models (GBDT and XGB), was used sequentially on the dataset. In doing so, a detailed evaluation was

Table 2 Model accuracies and fairness of the models assessed using DI for "two_year_recid" and "is_recid" with protected variables (Sex and Race)

Metrics	LogReg	SVC	GBDT	XGB
Accuracies (Target: "two_yr_recid")	68.88	69.50	68.81	68.88
Accuracies (Target: "is_recid")	67.42	68.46	68.39	66.87
Initial DI (PV: Sex)	3.2615	1.8615	2.1701	1.9409
Initial DI (PV: Race)	0.4504	0.5546	0.5019	0.4610

ensured such that it accounts for multiple approaches to predictive performance as well as fairness, with each model contributing its own unique strengths to the analysis.

3 Implementation

3.1 Explainability Tools

Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) are the methods and techniques in machine learning that make the predictions of the AI models more understandable to humans. The primary objective is to give an insight into how and why a model is coming to a specific decision, something that is critical for guaranteeing trust and transparency in AI systems. XAI allows us to comprehend the relationship between inputs (features) and outputs (predictions), which allows us to make more informed decisions and detect potential biases. In this study, the primary goal of employing XAI (Explainable Artificial Intelligence) tools was to determine which features most impact the models and determine the potential biases. This work mostly deals with SHAP and Fairlearn as XAI tools.

SHAP is implemented for three of the four models under consideration in the study: XGBoost (XGB), Logistic Regression (LogReg) and Gradient Boosted Classifier. For LogReg, LinearExplainer is utilized, whereas for XGB and GBC, the Explainer default included in the SHAP documentation is utilized. SHAP does not support SVC natively, therefore it is not considered in the analysis. (SHAP results are shown in the Fig. 8, Fig. 9 and Fig. 10).

Fig. 8 SHAP plots for XGBoost with is_recid and two_year_recid

Fig. 9 SHAP plots for Logistic Regression with is_recid and two_year_recid

Fig. 10 SHAP plots for Gradient Boosted Classifier with `is_recid` and `two_year_recid`

Among the features evaluated, the most important predictor of recidivism across all models is `priors_count`. Higher prior offences, as indicated by the red regions in SHAP plots, increase the likelihood of re-offending. Gradient Boosting Decision Trees and XGBoost exhibit strong nonlinear effects for this feature, whereas Logistic Regression displays a more linear relationship. Age is also a significant determining factor: young individuals (`age_18-25`, `age_26-35`) have a higher risk of recidivism, while older people (`age_46+`) are less likely to reoffend. Logistic Regression more clearly reinforces the influence of age compared to the tree-based models.

In terms of gender, men are more likely to reoffend than women. In terms of race, `race_African-American` is significantly positively associated with recidivism, as shown by SHAP analysis, suggesting that African-Americans have greater chances of recidivism prediction. On the other hand, `race_Caucasian`, `race_Hispanic`, and other races have lesser contributions to predictions. Juvenile crimes, especially juvenile felonies, also significantly contribute to a greater chance of recidivism, whereas misdemeanour charges have lesser impact. Logistic Regression tends to overestimate the effect of juvenile crimes more than tree-based models.

FairLearn results for all four models considered in the study are shown in Table 3, Table 4, Table 5 and Table 6. Inspection of Table 3 and Table 6 indicates a uniform pattern of imbalance in inaccuracy among protected demographic categories that suggests the need for compensation against bias in default machine learning classifiers to the application of recidivism prediction tasks. Table 3 and Table 4 give the fairness analysis among different classifiers—XGBoost (XGB), Support Vector Classification (SVC), Gradient Boosted Classifier (GBC), and Logistic Regression—and “Sex (Male)” as the given protected attribute. Based on targets `Is_recid` and `Two_year_recid`, there are considerable differences in group-specific accuracies. For

example, Table 3 indicates that SVC is 72.40% accurate in non-male group (Var = 0) but just 68.14% accurate in male group (Var = 1), and that XGB and GBC also indicate analogous differences.

Table 5 and Table 6 transfer the focus to “Race (African American)” as the protected variable. Table 5 indicates that for `Two_year_recid` prediction, SVC achieves accuracy of 69.10% for non-African Americans whereas only 65.35% for African Americans—a gigantic fairness gap. GBC and XGB also follow the same trend, with differences in group-wise accuracy of roughly 2–3%. Table 6 illustrates that for `Is_recid` prediction, while gaps are narrower, the problem persists; XGB, for instance, achieves an accuracy of 67.97% for non-African Americans and 66.66% for African Americans.

The findings obtained by Fairlearn’s group-wise analysis on average reveal that although the classifiers have the same overall accuracy metrics, they behave differently when measured in terms of different genders and racial groups. The discovery lends credence to the notion that machine learning algorithms of the standard variety—when applied in isolation—are also likely to perpetuate and even amplify societal biases, thus providing justification for fairness-based methods in high-stakes applications such as criminal justice.

Table 3 Fairlearn Accuracy metrics for different models with protected variable Sex (Var = Sex Male)

Protected Variable Models \ Metrics	Is_recid		
	Overall Accuracy	Accuracy by Group	
		Var = 0	Var = 1
XGBoost (XGB)	67.29	70.40	66.63
Support Vector Classification (SVC)	68.88	72.40	68.14
Gradient Boosted Classifier (GBC)	67.84	72.00	67.64
Logistic Regression	68.39	70.40	67.30

Table 4 Fairlearn Accuracy metrics for different models with protected variable Sex (Var = Sex Male)

Protected Variable Models \ Metrics	Two_year_recid		
	Overall Accuracy	Accuracy by Group	
		Var = 0	Var = 1
XGBoost (XGB)	67.35	69.60	66.89
Support Vector Classification (SVC)	69.23	72.00	68.65
Gradient Boosted Classifier (GBC)	69.09	69.60	68.06
Logistic Regression	68.32	69.60	68.06

Table 5 Fairlearn Accuracy metrics for different models with protected variable Race (Var = Race African American)

Protected Variable Models \ Metrics	Two_year_recid		
	Overall Accuracy	Accuracy by Group Var = 0 Var = 1	
XGBoost (XGB)	67.35	68.25	66.48
Support Vector Classification (SVC)	69.23	69.10	69.35
Gradient Boosted Classifier (GBC)	68.32	68.11	68.53
Logistic Regression	69.09	69.24	68.94

Table 6 Fairlearn Accuracy metrics for different models with protected variable Race (Var = Race African American)

Protected Variable Models \ Metrics	Is_recid		
	Overall Accuracy	Accuracy by Group Var = 0 Var = 1	
XGBoost (XGB)	67.29	67.97	66.66
Support Vector Classification (SVC)	68.88	68.82	68.94
Gradient Boosted Classifier (GBC)	68.39	69.38	67.44
Logistic Regression	67.84	67.83	67.85

3.2 Fairness Techniques

Up to this point, it has been concluded that none of the four machine learning models, when used independently, are fair (Tolan et al. 2019). This is primarily because the models, when trained solely to optimize for accuracy, tend to replicate and even amplify existing societal biases present in historical data. Additionally, fairness metrics such as disparate impact and equal opportunity difference consistently revealed significant gaps across protected groups. To mitigate the bias, three additional methods: pre-processing, in-processing, and post-processing. In this research, the pre-processing method was skipped, as described in the datasets section, because the dataset is unbiased and pre-processed, with an equal distribution for both the target variables: is_recid and two_year_recid. All the models were implemented separately in three configurations: stand-alone in-processing, stand-alone post-processing and both in-processing and post-processing (Chen et al. 2023).

3.2.1 Stand-alone In-processing Techniques

In-processing methods are the fairness techniques applied during the model training process. Three techniques available are: Prejudice Remover, Adversarial Debiasing, Meta Fair Classifier. This research has only considered the Adversarial Debiasing method (Zhang et al. 2018) as the Prejudice Remover method computed an accuracy of 3.78%, leading to its exclusion. The Meta fair classifier was excluded because it only

works for binary sensitive attributes, such as (Male v/s Female) and not for multi-class sensitive attributes, such as Race, in this research. It also can only be implemented on linear models like Logistic Regression and not on non-linear models like SVC, GBC and XGB in this research. Hence, to compare all the models on the same measure, this technique was excluded.

Adversarial methods have before been used for bias mitigation (Wadsworth et al. 2018). The Adversarial Debiasing method, an in-processing technique, is used during the training of machine learning models to reduce the potential bias. It introduces an additional model, namely the “adversary”, which tries to predict the sensitive attribute from the model’s predictions. The main model is trained in such a manner to make predictions by fooling the adversary into thinking it cannot predict the sensitive feature. In this way, the model is encouraged to learn to make accurate predictions without relying on biased attributes, thus reducing unfairness. The results were then recorded as shown in Table 7.

Table 7 Disparate Impact values of the models using Adversarial Debiasing for both, Sex and Race

Protected Variable Models \ Metrics	Sex		Race	
	Accuracy	DI	Accuracy	DI
XGBoost (XGB)	67.15	0.8400	66.52	1.030
Support Vector Classification (SVC)	68.26	0.9973	66.94	0.9308
Gradient Boosted Classifier (GBC)	68.26	0.9973	66.80	1.318
Logistic Regression	68.74	1.200	66.73	1.1615

From the analysis, it can be inferred that for “Sex” as the protected variable, XGBoost (XGB) yields the best performance with an competitive accuracy of 67.15% and the lowest Disparate Impact (DI) value of 0.84, indicating a relatively low bias in comparison to other models. SVC and GBC both exhibit similar performance, with a higher accuracy of 68.26% and slightly higher DI value of 0.9973. Logistic Regression, while giving the highest accuracy of 68.74% , also demonstrates the highest DI of 1.2. When comparing all the models, SVC and GBC turn out to be the best performers, showing a high accuracy with a DI value close to 1 (0.9973). Logistic Regression, although giving a higher DI accuracy, suggests slightly higher bias in its predictions compared to SVC and GBC, due to its highest DI value. XGB, despite having the lowest DI, also demonstrates a lower accuracy, indicating that it is under-fit.

For “Race” as the protected variable, the analysis clearly shows that Support Vector Classifier (SVC) performs the best, achieving the highest accuracy of 66.94% and lowest DI value of 0.9308, which is closer to 1, indicating it to be the fairest model. In contrast, the other models, XGB, GBC and Logistic Regression exhibit lower accuracies (66.52, 66.80 and 66.73, respectively) and higher DI value (1.0300,1.1318 and 1.1615, respectively), indicating that they are biased in their predictions.

3.2.2 Stand-alone Post-processing Techniques

Post-processing techniques are fairness techniques applied after the model has made its predictions. Here also there are 3 techniques, namely: Reject Option Classification (ROC), Calibrated Equalized Odds (CEO), and Equalized Odds Post-processing (EO).

ROC (Kamiran et al. 2012), a post-processing fairness method implemented after the model has given its output. It works by identifying the predictions that the model is uncertain about and rejects them. These uncertain outputs are neglected in decision-making, which helps to avoid biased outcomes. ROC focuses on ensuring that the model’s predictions are fair by limiting the impact of the uncertain outputs that might be biased or inaccurate.

CEO (Pleiss et al. 2017), another post-processing technique, ensures that the model’s errors (i.e., false positives and false negatives) are equally distributed among different categories (such as race or sex). In simple words, the model has the same probability to make an error for all the categories, leading to more fair outcomes. CEO, hence, works by adjusting the decision threshold for each group, making sure that the model’s outputs are balanced across the categories.

EO (Hardt et al. 2016), also a post-processing method, makes sure that the model’s false positive and false negative rates are equal for different groups. This means that the model shouldn’t unfairly favour one group over another when it makes wrong predictions. EO adjusts the model’s outcomes after they are made to correct any imbalance in how errors are distributed among the groups.

Table 8 Accuracy and DI of models with Adversarial Debiasing and Post-Processing methods for protected attribute Sex

Post-Processing Methods	Evaluation Type	XGB	SVC	LogReg	GBDT
ROC	DI	1.9409	1.8615	3.2615	2.1701
	Acc.	66.87	68.46	67.42	68.26
EO	DI	1.0875	1.1068	1.0947	1.0957
	Acc.	62.37	66.59	60.56	64.17
CEO	DI	2.2769	2.1479	3.4378	2.5105
	Acc.	66.66	68.19	67.42	67.98

The above Table 8 and Table 9 show the fairness and the accuracy performance of above four classification models with respect to the protected variables Sex and Race, respectively. The analysis focused on three alternative post-processing approaches: Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC), Equalized Odds (EO), and Calibrated Equalized Odds (CEO), as previously outlined.

In accuracy of prediction, Support Vector Classification (SVC) performed best at an accuracy rate of 68.46%, followed by Gradient Boosted Decision Trees (GBDT) at an accuracy rate of 68.26%. The XGBoost (XGB) model, however, recorded the lowest Disparate Impact (DI) of 1.9409 with a slightly lower accuracy of 66.87%. The DI for Logistic Regression was significantly higher at 3.2615, indicating a very

Table 9 Accuracy and DI of all models with Adversarial Debiasing and Post-Processing methods for protected attribute Race

Post-Processing Methods	Evaluation Type	XGB	SVC	LogReg	GBDT
ROC	DI	0.4610	0.5546	0.4504	0.5019
	Acc.	66.87	68.46	67.42	68.26
EO	DI	0.9114	0.8832	0.9063	0.9062
	Acc.	61.26	63.68	62.02	62.57
CEO	DI	0.4301	0.5489	0.4474	0.4585
	Acc.	66.66	68.32	67.35	68.19

high gender-based disparity in predictions. This outcome suggests that while SVC is a better-performing model in accuracy, XGB is less biased in predictions. However, SVC remains the most equitable choice when it comes to fairness as well as general performance.

When compared on Equalized Odds, SVC once again excelled with the best balance of accuracy (66.59%) and fairness (DI of 1.1068). XGB, on the other hand, lost its accuracy (62.37%) under this measure despite having a good DI (1.0875). Logistic Regression and GBDT exhibited the lowest accuracies (60.56% and 64.17%, respectively), while Logistic Regression also exhibited a good level of fairness with a DI of 1.0947. But these models compromised accuracy for fairness, and SVC was the best pick under this approach of evaluation too.

In the last measure of assessment, SVC retained its best performance status, with an accuracy level of 68.19% and a Disparity Index (DI) of 2.1479. While the latter, higher than those found in ROC and EO, is still a fairly just level of equity. XGB and GBDT both had relatively similar performance indices, with 66.66% and 67.98% accuracies, respectively, but the corresponding models were associated with high DIs, indicating higher disparity in their predictive values. Logistic Regression still demonstrated the highest DI of 3.4378 with a relatively modest accuracy of 67.42%, thus cementing its relatively high bias.

3.2.3 Combination of In-processing & Post-processing Techniques

The Table 10 and Table 11 represent the Accuracies and Disparate Impact values of all the machine learning models, when applied with both in-processing (Adversarial Debiasing) and post-processing (Reject Option Classifier (ROC), Equalized Odds (EO), Calibrated Equalized Odds (CEO)) fairness techniques, considering both the protected variables, Race and Sex, respectively.

For sex as the protected attribute, Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) analysis identified Support Vector Classifier (SVC) as the top-performing model. It delivered the highest accuracy of 68.26% while having a Disparate Impact (DI) of 1.0012 – closest to the best fairness ratio of 1.0—showing very little bias of predictions between sex groups. Even Logistic Regression had an equal accuracy of 68.74% but a higher DI of 1.1320, indicating higher disparity. XGBoost also had a lower accuracy of 66.38% with a DI of 0.9273, reflecting lower performance and slight bias. GBDT also had an equal

Table 10 Accuracy and DI of all models using In-processing and Post-Processing Methods for Sex as the protected feature

Post-Processing Methods	Evaluation Type	XGB	SVC	LogReg	GBDT
ROC	DI	0.9273	1.0012	1.1320	1.0012
	Acc.	66.38	68.26	68.74	68.26
EO	DI	1.0649	1.0788	1.1001	1.0788
	Acc.	64.72	65.07	68.05	65.07
CEO	DI	0.8709	1.4555	1.6990	1.4555
	Acc.	67.42	68.39	68.81	68.39

Table 11 Accuracy and DI of all models using In-processing and Post-Processing Methods for Race as the protected feature

Post-Processing Methods	Evaluation Type	XGB	SVC	LogReg	GBDT
ROC	DI	0.9111	0.9163	0.9582	0.9190
	Acc.	66.94	67.22	67.15	67.08
EO	DI	0.8926	0.8905	0.8938	0.8953
	Acc.	64.93	65.34	65.07	66.18
CEO	DI	0.7504	0.7638	0.7681	0.9251
	Acc.	66.38	66.94	66.38	66.73

accuracy to SVC (68.26%) but with much higher DI of 2.1701, reflecting high disparity. Thus, SVC provided the optimal compromise between fairness and predictive ability here.

In the Equalized Odds (EO) assessment, SVC was again most accurate (65.07%) with a DI of 1.0788, being most balanced both in fairness and in accuracy. XGB dropped slightly in accuracy (64.72%) but was still highly balanced with a DI of 1.0649. Logistic Regression was the lowest in accuracy (63.28%) with a DI of 1.1001, and thus has lesser accuracy as well as more disparity.

Under Calibrated Equalized Odds (CEO) evaluation, SVC again demonstrated the highest accuracy (68.39%) but with a higher DI of 1.4555. XGB, on the other hand, demonstrated a good balance with accuracy at 67.42% and a lower DI of 0.8709, thus being the most equitable and accurate model in this evaluation. Logistic Regression was accurate at 67.42%, but its DI was the highest at 1.6990, which reflected a huge imbalance in its predictions.

For Race, in ROC analysis, SVC again had the highest accuracy (67.22%) with a DI of 0.9163. XGB had the same accuracy of 66.94% but a slightly lower DI (0.9111), indicating slightly less bias. Logistic Regression had a higher DI (0.9582) and lower accuracy (67.15%), indicating a higher degree of bias in its predictions. GBDT was the same with an accuracy of 67.08% and a DI of 0.9190.

In the Equalized Odds (EO) assessment, SVC had the highest accuracy (65.34%) with a DI of 0.8905, and a good balance between fairness and prediction performance.

XGB had a lower accuracy (64.93%) but still a low DI of 0.8926. Logistic Regression and GBDT had lower accuracies (65.07% and 66.18%, respectively), with similar DIs, and thus were not the best options for race as a protected feature.

In the Calibrated Equalized Odds (CEO) analysis, SVC was doing great with 66.94% accuracy and a low DI of 0.7638, maintaining its consistent performance across all aspects. XGB came close with 66.38% accuracy and a DI of 0.7504, demonstrating its trade-off between fairness and accuracy. Logistic Regression still had the maximum DI (0.7681) with identical accuracy (66.36%).

4 Results & Discussions

4.1 Results

In order to assess the models, this study focused on two primary aspects: fairness and predictive power. Accuracy was employed as the main performance metric, measuring the number of correct predictions (true positives and true negatives) relative to the total number of predictions. However, due to the typically imbalanced nature of the dataset—where the number of non-recidivists can significantly exceed the number of recidivists—accuracy alone was deemed potentially misleading. Therefore, this research also incorporated additional evaluation metrics such as precision, recall, F1-score, and the classification report to provide a more comprehensive assessment of the models’ performance.

For the evaluation of fairness, this study utilized the concept of disparate impact to determine whether the models exhibited bias against specific demographic groups, particularly in terms of race and sex. Disparate impact is calculated as the ratio of positive outcomes for unprivileged groups to those for privileged groups. A ratio below 0.8 suggests biased predictions against unprivileged groups, while a ratio above 1.2 may indicate preferential treatment toward these groups. A ratio close to 1.0 is considered ideal, signifying that the model behaves fairly and consistently across different demographic groups.

$$\text{Disparate Impact} = \frac{\text{Selection Rate of Protected Variable}}{\text{Selection Rate of Non-Protected Variable}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{True Positives} + \text{True Negatives}}{\text{Total population}} \quad (2)$$

According to the performance of all four models - XGBoost (XGB), Support Vector Classifier (SVC), Logistic Regression and Gradient Boosting Classifier (GBC) - with regard to both accuracy and fairness for Sex and Race as protected attribute, Support Vector Classifier (SVC) is the most appropriate model in general for predicting recidivism. It fared well for both Sex and Race as protected variables with good balance between accuracy and Disparate Impact (DI) values, being fair and least biased in predictions with high performance. SVC had consistent high accuracy, particularly when Equalized Odds (EO) and Calibrated Equalized Odds (CEO) fairness measures were employed, where it registered an accuracy of 65.34% and 66.94% and DI values of 0.8905 and 0.7638, respectively. The DI values were quite low, indicating

that SVC is fair in both sex and race-based predictions while having a good predictive performance.

XGBoost demonstrated competitive fairness values of 0.8400 (Sex) and 1.030 (Race), but was behind in accuracy (66.52% for Race and 66.87% under ROC). While XGB performed better on fairness, its comparatively lower accuracy than SVC means that it is less suitable for the real-world situation where accuracy matters.

Logistic Regression, although it has the highest accuracy for Sex (68.74%), had the largest DI value 1.200 for Sex and 1.615 for Race, showing high bias in predictions. Despite its high accuracy, the model’s high DI indicates high bias, rendering it inappropriate for situations requiring fairness as well as accuracy.

Gradient Boosting Classifier (GBC) showed comparable results to Logistic Regression, with similar accuracy (68.26%) but showed higher DI values (1.4555) under CEO for Sex and 1.1318 for Race, which shows a greater level of bias than SVC and XGB. This performance indicates that, although GBC is good competition in terms of accuracy, its fairness is compromised, so it is less optimal than SVC.

Table 12 shows the Disparate Impact Values for all the implementation methods of all the machine learning models with respect to “Sex”

Models/Process	AD	ROC	EO	CEO	AD+ROC	AD+EO	AD+CEO
XGB	0.84	1.9409	1.0875	2.2769	0.9273	1.0649	0.8709
SVM	0.9973	1.8615	1.1068	2.1479	1.0012	1.0788	1.4555
LogReg	0.9973	3.2615	1.0947	3.4378	1.132	1.1001	1.6999
GBC	1.2	2.1701	1.0957	2.5105	1.0012	1.0788	1.4555

Table 13 shows the Disparate Impact Values for all the implementation methods of all the machine learning models with respect to “Race”

Models/Process	AD	ROC	EO	CEO	AD+ROC	AD+EO	AD+CEO
XGB	1.03	0.461	0.9114	0.4301	0.9111	0.8926	0.7504
SVM	0.9308	0.5546	0.8832	0.5489	0.9163	0.8905	0.7638
LogReg	1.1318	0.4504	0.9063	0.4474	0.9582	0.8938	0.7681
GBC	1.1615	0.5019	0.9062	0.4585	0.919	0.8953	0.9251

Fig. 11 Accuracy and DI of all models with In-Processing and Post-Processing methods for the protected attribute Sex

Fig. 12 Accuracy and DI of all models with In-Processing and Post-Processing methods for the protected attribute Race

Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 display the performance of some fairness mitigation techniques when implemented with four classifiers—XGBoost (XGB), Support Vector Classifier (SVC), Logistic Regression (LR), and Gradient Boosting Classifier (GBC)—tested on the basis of Sex and Race. In both instances, SVC repeatedly shows the overall best trade-off between accuracy and fairness.

In Fig. 11 (Sex), SVC obtains the highest or second-highest accuracies in all but most configurations, especially in ROC, CEO, AD+RO, and AD+CEO, with low values of Disparate Impact (DI) as well—especially in AD+EO and AD+ROC, where DI is just short of the ideal value of 1. SVC is noteworthy in that it does not fall into the extreme fairness violations observed by LR for the CEO strategy, with DI jumping enormously.

Likewise, in Fig. 12 (Race), SVC maintains its robust performance, indicating robust accuracy under ROC, CEO, and AD+CEO approaches. Noticeably, its DI values remain tightly clustered close to 1 in all strategies, reflecting well-balanced and

fair predictions. These findings make SVC the strongest contender for guaranteeing fairness at the cost of not sacrificing predictive accuracy in recidivism prediction.

Overall, the Support Vector Classifier (SVC) offers the optimal balance between aggregate accuracy and fairness among the models tested in this research. It shows robust predictive quality across various fairness methods, holding high accuracy consistently with low bias. The model’s capability to demonstrate insensitivity to fairness method variations like Adversarial Debiasing (AD), Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC), Equalized Odds (EO), and Calibrated Equalized Odds (CEO) showcases its strength in maintaining both fairness and accuracy. Additionally, the Disparate Impact (DI) scores for SVC were consistently low, reflecting its capability to make fair predictions with negligible disparity among protected groups. This blend of good prediction accuracy and lower bias is what makes SVC the best alternative for predicting recidivism in this study since it does not only produce precise results but is also fair over sensitive variables like Sex and Race. As such, SVC emerges as the most appropriate model in that it comes up with a credible solution for the challenge posed by the recidivism predictability and overcomes biases against the decision.

4.2 Future Work

The objective of the current study was to minimize bias through adversarial debiasing alone as the single in-processing method. For future studies, there can be other in-processing methods like Prejudice Remover Regularizer, Meta Fair Classifier, or GerryFair Classifier. For future studies, casual fairness methods such as counterfactual fairness and structural causal models can also be involved. The fairness interventions used here can be cross-checked on other sensitive decision-making datasets such as the Adult Income, German Credit, or Law School datasets. This will help to verify the generalizability and robustness of fairness approaches across domains. Subsequent work can extend the scope to include additional or intersectional protected attributes such as age, socioeconomic status, mental health status, or geographic region. This would contribute to a wider understanding of bias and its impact. Temporal information can help evaluate how fairness varies over time. Longitudinal follow-up of people can establish whether long-term outcomes are more or less fair than short-term outcomes.

Glossary

Adversarial Debiasing (AD):

A method that trains the model to be precise with minimal bias using an adversary.

Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC):

The ROC method is applied as a post-processing assessment method in order to evaluate classifier performance at different thresholds using the True Positive Rate (TPR) against the False Positive Rate (FPR).

<i>Equalized Odds (EO):</i>	A fairness constraint where equal true positive rates and false positive rates are enforced across various sensitive groups.
<i>Calibrated Equalized Odds (CEO):</i>	A post-processing fairness method that preserves probabilistic calibration while being fair.
<i>XGBoost (XGB):</i>	A high-performance gradient boosting framework widely applied to classification problems.
<i>Gradient Boosting Classifier (GBC):</i>	An ensemble learning technique that constructs trees sequentially to reduce classification errors.
<i>Support Vector Classifier (SVC):</i>	A supervised machine learning model that discriminates between classes along the best hyperplane.
<i>Logistic Regression (LogReg):</i>	A statistical binary classification model that makes probability estimates through the logistic function.
<i>Disparate Impact (DI):</i>	A fairness metric quantifying the ratio of desirable outcomes among unprivileged and privileged groups; a value close to 1 reflects fairness.
<i>Accuracy (Acc):</i>	The ratio of correct predictions made by a model to the total number of predictions.
<i>SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP):</i>	An XAI game theory-based model-agnostic approach that assigns an individual feature contribution to a prediction.
<i>Fairlearn:</i>	A Python library that allows fairness evaluation and mitigation for ML models based on various metrics like EO and DI.
<i>Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI):</i>	A set of techniques whose goal is to render the inner workings and decisions of ML models understandable and transparent to humans.

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Code availability The code is made publicly available at <https://github.com/Aagnya-Mistry/Bias-Mitigation-in-ML-Models-for-Recidivism>.

Declarations

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